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HUBRISTIC MOTIVATION OF HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS

The paper characterizes the structure of teaching activity motivation in high school teachers, which includes the hubristic aspiration for perfection and hubristic aspiration for superiority, different ways of pedagogical self-regulation (intrinsic motive, identification, introjected and extrinsic regulation), career orientations on professional competence, management, serving, entrepreneurship, challenge, management, integration of life styles, autonomy, on the stability of work and residence, professional motives (the motives of activity and self-realization, acknowledgment motive, acceptance motive, cognitive motive, the motive of livelihoods).

Keywords: pedagogical self-regulation, intrinsic self-regulation, identification, introjected and external regulation, hubristic motivation, career orientation, professional motives.

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ГУБРИСТИЧНА МОТИВАЦІЯ ВИКЛАДАЧІВ ВИЩОЇ ШКОЛИ

Стаття характеризує структуру мотивації педагогічної діяльності вчителів вищої школи, яка включає в себе губристичне прагнення до досконалості та прагнення до переваги, різні способи педагогічної саморегуляції (внутрішній мотив, ідентифікацію, інтроєктовану та зовнішню регуляцію), кар'єрні орієнтації на професійну компетентність, управління, обслуговування, підприємництво, виклик, управління, інтеграцію стилів життя, автономію, стабільність роботи та місця проживання, професійні мотиви (мотиви діяльності та самореалізації, мотив визнання, мотив прийняття, пізнавальний мотив, мотив засобів до існування). Розкрито кореляційні зв'язки губристичної мотивації з показниками професійної мотивації викладачів вищої школи.

Ключові слова: педагогічна саморегуляція, внутрішня саморегуляція, ідентифікація, інтроєктоване та зовнішнє регулювання, губристична мотивація, кар'єрні орієнтації, професійні мотиви.

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ГУБРИСТИЧЕСКАЯ МОТИВАЦИЯ ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЕЙ ВЫСШЕЙ ШКОЛЫ

В статье охарактеризована структура мотивации педагогической деятельности преподавателей высшей школы, которая включает в себя губристическое стремление к совершенству и стремление к превосходству, различные способы педагогической саморегуляции (внутренний мотив, идентификацию, интроецированную и внешнюю регуляцию), карьерные ориентации на профессиональную компетентность, управление, служение, предпринимательство, вызов, управление, интеграцию стилей жизни, автономию, стабильность работы и места жительства, профессиональные мотивы (мотивы деятельности и самореализации, мотив признания, мотив принятия, познавательный мотив, мотивацию достижения средств к существованию). Раскрыты корреляционные связи губристической мотивации с показателями профессиональной мотивации преподавателей высшей школы.

Ключевые слова: педагогическая саморегуляция, внутренняя саморегуляция, идентификация, интроецированная и внешняя регуляция, губристическая мотивация, карьерные ориентации, профессиональные мотивы.

Introduction. Nowadays the problem of motivation and self-regulation of professional activity of high school teachers seems particularly relevant in connection with the need to ensure the success of the professional, the psychological support of their professional functions.

In pedagogical science, the most developed are the research of pedagogical activity in the context of teacher's pedagogical skills (Yu.P. Azarov, B.G. Ananiev, Yu.K. Babansky, I.A. Zyazyun, E.M. Pavlyutenkov, M.M. Potashnik, N.V. Tarasevich, E.V. Tkachenko), pedagogical creativity (V.I. Zagvyazinsky, V.A. Kan-Kalik, N.D. Nikandrov, I.P. Rachenko), professional self-education of the teacher (A.J. Aret, S.B. Yelakanov), structures of pedagogical activity (E.F. Zeyer, I.A. Zimnya, N.V. Kukharev, L.M. Mitina, etc.).

The problem of research and development of the characteristics of a competitive high school teacher was studied by Zh.B. Shajamakova [11]. According to the author, it is necessary to study the psychological peculiarities of his professional activity in the broadest sense (presented in the studies of O.M. Leontiev, A. Matyushkin, A.S. Romanova, S.L. Rubinstein) and in the context of self-improvement (disclosed in the works of S.I. Arkhangelskii, V.A. Slastonin, L.S. Podimova, V.A. Sitarova, N.V. Kuzmina, V.A. Popkova, A.V. Korzhuyev, etc.), as well as the professional competence (T.I. Dotsevych, Z.F. Yesarev, A.L. Busygin, M.A. Choshanov).

The structure of the pedagogical orientation, self-awareness and self-development of the teacher of the university is presented in the works of E.F. Zeier, E.P. Ilyin, G.A. Karpova, L.M. Mitina, O.V. Moskalenko.

The specifics of the professional and pedagogical activity of high school teachers are revealed in the studies of V.N. Abrosimov, Z.F. Yesarev, V.G. Ivanova, B.B. Imashev, I.A. Zimnaya, T.I. Rudneva, G.I. Sanzhar,

N.M. Talanchuk. The problem of training and retraining of teachers of higher education is presented in the works of T.I. Dotsevych, L.I. Gurier, B.D. Dzhandorbenko, V. Zhukov, V.G. Ivanov, A.A. Kirsanov, J.A. Kudryavtsev, N.Yu. Postaluk, V.S. Sokolova, R. Dive, E. Gelli, P. Legrand, and others. In the system of continuous education, the problem of teacher training was violated in the studies G.U. Matushansky, and E.M. Khanafina.

The motivational component of a person's readiness for teaching is appropriate to consider, based on the types of professional activity of the teacher higher education institution, as a unity of motivation for pedagogical and scientific activity. The structure of the motivation of pedagogical activity, according to T.P. Prikhodko, make up grounds for binding; motives of achievement; motives of interest and enthusiasm for the subject being taught; motives for engaging with students (affiliation motives) [8].

In order to ensure a positive professional motivation of teachers of higher educational institutions in the process of professional activity should be as fully as possible to determine the factors that influence the formation of a person's motivational complex. That is, it is necessary to take into account the motives for updating the internal motives of professional activity and satisfying the professional needs of the subject of activity. For this purpose, it is necessary to study the peculiarities and dynamics of the development of professional motivation. The definition of demotivating factors that block the implementation of the needs of teachers and their consideration during the formation of professional motivation will also contribute to ensuring positive results in the development of motivation in professional activity [10].

Self-regulation in activity provides the key role in professional motivation. According to self-determination theory, Edward L. Deci and Richard M. Ryan [9] determine four levels of motivation: 1) external or extrinsic (behavior and activity are regulated with rewards and punishments); 2) introjection (behavior is regulated with partly adopted rules and requirements); 3) identification (behavior is regulated with sense of own choice of this activity, managed previously from outside); 4) internal or intrinsic (interest to activity). According to this conception, exactly the intrinsic motivation, based on the inherent requirements in a competence (choice of optimum difficulty of tasks, presence of positive feedback) and self-determination (autonomy, internality of personality), determines the success in studying [7].

T.I. Dotsevych developed the concept of pedagogical self-regulation. Pedagogical self-regulation a psychological phenomenon that reveals the motivational orientation of the teacher of higher education for the optimal implementation of his or her own professional activity and is realized through the key incentives (internal motivation as an interest in teaching activities; external

motivation as a desire to avoid punishment, identification as a result of a teacher comparing himself with other colleagues and the teaching values; introjected regulation as a conviction that there is a certain set of things that must do the teacher). The high level of pedagogical self-regulation, in particular the superiority of internal motivation in its structure, involves the development of meta-cognitive awareness and high abnovity of the teacher of higher education [1].

According to J. Kozielicki hubristic motivation is conceived as a cluster of motives that make people assert and enhance their self-worth (self-importance, self-esteem). By transgressive behavior we mean any behavior whose outcome goes beyond the boundaries of the individual's past accomplishments (e.g., territorial expansion, enhancement of power, broadening of personal freedom, or development of new scientific theories) [2]. The research of motivational stricter of K.I. Fomenko shows, that there are relations between intrinsic motive and the pursuit of perfection and between extrinsic motive and the commitment to excellence and power [5]. The problem of hubristic motivation of high school teachers hasn't examined in contemporary psychology.

The **aim** of the article is to determine the motivational structure of professional activity of and the role of hubristic motivation in professional motivation of high school teachers.

Research methods. The following techniques were used in the study: 1) The psychodiagnostics of hubristic motivation [6]; 2) Pedagogical self-regulation Questionnaire (T.I. Dotsevych) [1]; 3) The Career orientations Questionnaire "Career Anchors" (author – Edgar Schein) [3]; 4) "Motives of professional activity Questionnaire" (author – T. M. Frantseva) [4]. The study also used the original questionnaire of self-regulation of labor activity, standardization of which is described below.

The **sample** included 153 high school teachers (121 women and 32 men). Research sample based on State Higher Educational Establishment «Donbass State Pedagogical University», Sloviansk, Ukraine.

Discussion. There is a positive correlation between pedagogical self-regulation and a *hubristic motivation*: between the indicators of aspiration for perfection and internal motivation ($r=0,34$, $p<0,0001$) and identification ($r=0,23$, $p<0,001$). Consequently, the autonomous pedagogical self-regulation, due to the internal motives of teaching activity and identification, is associated with the aspiration for perfection and improvement of skill.

There are correlations between the indicators of aspiration for perfection and such *career orientations* as professional competence ($r=0,69$, $p<0,0001$), management ($r=0,16$, $p<0,05$), service ($r=0,18$, $p<0,05$), challenge ($r=0,23$, $p<0,001$), the integration of lifestyles ($r=0,19$, $p<0,05$). Interest in teaching activity and striving for mastering in it provide career orientations to mastering professional competence, management in an organization, service to the goals

and mission of a chosen profession, assistance to people, acceptance of professional challenges and competition.

There are negative correlations between the indicators of aspiration for superiority and the career orientations on professional competence ($r=-0,18$, $p<0,05$), orientation on stability of work ($r=-0,19$, $p<0,05$), and on service ($r=-0,19$, $p<0,05$). There are positive correlations between indicators of aspiration for superiority and the career orientations on management ($r=0,55$, $p<0,0001$) and autonomous orientation ($r=0,58$, $p<0,0001$).

There are statistically significant relationships between hubristic motivation and the *motives of professional activity*, which suggests that the desire for honest performance of activity and striving to be better than others is related to professional motives. Aspiration for perfection is positively related to cognitive motive ($r=0,40$, $p<0,0001$), activity motive ($r=0,52$, $p<0,0001$) and self-realization motive ($r=0,49$, $p<0,0001$). Thus, striving for mastering in professional activity suggests the professional interest, high level of activity and the desire of self-realization. There are negative correlations with the motive of livelihood ($r=-0,34$, $p<0,0001$), the motive of acknowledgment ($r=-0,28$, $p<0,0001$), the motive of interaction ($r=-0,32$, $p<0,0001$), thus the focus on glory and rewards excludes the desire to provide material life and to receive praise and acknowledgment as well as to interact with colleagues.

The aspiration for superiority has positive correlations with the motive of livelihood ($r=0,25$, $p<0,001$), the motive of interaction ($r=0,22$, $p<0,01$) and the motive of acknowledgment ($r=0,23$, $p<0,001$). There are negative correlations between the aspiration for superiority and cognitive motive ($r=-0,27$, $p<0,0001$), activity motive ($r=-0,41$, $p<0,0001$) and self-realization motive ($r=-0,21$, $p<0,01$). Thus, striving for superiority is connected with the desire to be rich, famous and to interact with other people. Teachers who strive for being better than others do not truly want to realize their potential and do not have interest in profession.

The next task of this study was to determine the structure of the motivation of teaching activity. The use of factor analysis showed that there are 6 factors that reveal the structure of the motivation of the person's teaching activity.

Factor 1 (14,5% of dispersion, 3,05 factor loading) created by indicators: career orientations on challenge (0,833), entrepreneurship (0,779), integration of life styles (0,703) and management (0,574). The psychological content of the motives that formed this factor reflects the «*High school teacher's career orientations*», which means the domination of a career orientation on challenges in professional activity.

Factor 2 (13% of dispersion, 2,72 factor loading) includes aspiration for perfection (0,817), career orientation on professional competence (0,765), the

motive of self-realization (0,704), the motive of activity (0,522), intrinsic motivation (0,418), acknowledgment motive (-0,462).

Table 1

The structure of the teaching activity motivation in high school teachers

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Factors</i>					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Hubristic aspiration for perfection		0,817				
Hubristic aspiration for superiority			-0,840			
Professional competence		0,765				
Management	0,574		-0,553			
Autonomy			-0,740			
Stability of work				-0,866		
Stability residence				-0,702		
Serving					0,521	
Challenge	0,833					
Integration of life styles	0,703					
Entrepreneurship	0,779					
The motive of livelihoods						0,765
The motive of interaction						
Cognitive motive			0,466		0,487	
The motive of activity		0,522	0,458			
Acknowledgment motive		-0,462				
The motive of self-realization		0,704				
Intrinsic motivation		0,418			0,577	
Identification					0,808	
Introjected regulation				-0,850		
External regulation						0,741
Factor loadings	3,051	2,724	2,377	2,340	1,892	1,504
% dispersion	0,145	0,129	0,113	0,111	0,090	0,071

The content of the indicators that formed the first factor indicates that it can be designated as a factor of the «*Aspiration for perfection in professional competence mastering*». It combines hubristic aspiration for perfection, the mastery of professional competence and skills, professional motives of self-realization and activity at job, high level of career motivation with interest in teaching activity, which acts as its internal regulator of professional duties.

Factor 3 (11,3% of dispersion, 2,37 factor loading) presented by the aspiration to superiority (-0,840), career orientation on autonomy (-0,740), management (-0,553), cognitive (0,466) and activity (0,458) motives. The psychological meaning of the motives that formed this factor reflects a «*Renunciation of superiority for teaching activity*», because the factor explains the combination of aspiration for superiority and management, which are neglected by teachers, with striving for professional mastering.

Factor 4 (9% of dispersion, 1,89 factor loading) combined the stability of work (-0,866), introjected regulation (-0,850), stability residence (-0,702). The psychological content of the points that reflects the «*Introjected regulation in career stability orientations*». It reveals the desire for diligent performance of professional duties, adherence to teaching standards along with orientation on stability in work and life.

Factor 5 (7,9% of dispersion, 1,89 factor loading) combined identification (0,808), intrinsic motivation (0,577), serving (0,521), cognitive motive (0,487). The psychological content of the indicators that formed this factor reflects the «*Professional interests*» namely the ability to find the sense of pedagogical activity, the understanding of mission on professional activity, the willingness to overcoming obstacles and problems in professional growth.

Factor 6 (7,1% of dispersion, 1,50 factor loading) combined the motive of livelihoods (0,765) and external regulation (0,741). The psychological content of this factor reflects the «*External regulation in teacher's livelihoods*». It reflects the combination of the motive of material provision with the dependence of regulation of teaching professional activity from awards and punishments.

Conclusions. Hubristic aspirations is a kind of motivation, which is related to professional motives of a person. Aspiration for perfection is connected with professional competence and intrinsic pedagogical regulation of high school teacher, aspiration for superiority is associated with striving for challenges and management.

The components of teaching activity motivation in high school teacher have determined, namely: 1) the motives of «*High school teacher's career orientations*», which includes the leading career orientations of high school teachers; 2) the motives of «*Aspiration for perfection in professional competence mastering*», which contains the aspiration for perfection, career orientation on professional competence, the motives of self-realization, activity and intrinsic motivation; 3) the motives of «*Renunciation of superiority for teaching activity*», which neglect the hubristic aspiration to superiority, career orientation on autonomy and management; 4) the motives of «*Introjected regulation in career stability orientations*», which supposes combination of introjected pedagogical regulation with career orientation on the stability of work and residence; 5) the motives of «*Professional interests*», which contains intrinsic motivation, career

orientation on serving and cognitive motive; 6) the motives of «External regulation in teacher's livelihoods», which includes external regulation and the motive of livelihoods.

The prospect of further research is the study of the motivation structure of teaching activity in various age and professional categories.

REFERENCES

1. Dotsevych T.I. (2014). Development and testing of the questionnaire on pedagogical self-regulation of the teacher of the higher school of sciences. Journal "Psychology and Personality", №2(6), Kiiiv-Poltava P. 163-174.
2. Kozielcecki J. (1987) The role of hubristic motivation in transgressive behavior. *New Ideas in Psychology*. Volume 5, Issue 3. P. 361-383. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0732-118X\(87\)90006-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0732-118X(87)90006-7)
3. Mogilevkin E.A. (2007) Career growth. Diagnostics, technologies, training. SPb: Speech. 336 p.
4. Frantseva T.N. (2010) Questionnaire for the diagnostics of the motives of professional activity of specialists. Bulletin of the Samara Humanitarian Academy. Series: Psychology. 2. P. 146-150.
5. Fomenko K.I. (2015) Hubristic motivation in the structure of the motivational sphere of individual of students. Collection of scientific works of the Institute H.S. Kostyuk. MNU V.O. Sukhomlinsky, Volume 7, Ecological Psychology. Issue 38. P. 444-454.
6. Fomenko K.I. (2015) Psychology of Success: A Study Guide. Kharkiv: "Disa plus". 274 p.
7. Deci E.L., Connell J.P., Ryan R.M. (1989). Self-determination in a work organization. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 74, 580-590.
8. Prikhodko T.P. (2012). Motivation of professional self-construction of the economic orientation as a component of his preparation for pedagogical activity in high school. *Effective economics*. №3. <http://www.economy.nayka.com.ua/?op=1&z=1011>
9. Ryan R., Deci E. L. (2000) Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivations: Classic Definitions and New Directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology* 25, 54-67.
10. Sevastianova J.V. (2011) Professional motivation of a teacher of a higher educational institution as a psychological problem Actual problems of psychology. University Krok. 10 Edition. P, 153-159.
11. Shajmakova Zh.B. (2009) The role of innovative competence in the development of the competitiveness of the teacher of higher education. Tambov. 248 p.